

KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS REGARDING DEMENTIA AMONG THE GENERAL ADULT POPULATION OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Dementia is a growing global health issue, with rising prevalence intensifying the need to understand public perceptions of its causes and care (WHO, 2021). In countries like Pakistan, where knowledge and awareness are particularly limited, misconceptions are even more pronounced.

Objective: To assess the awareness and understanding of dementia and its care among the general adult population of Pakistan. It seeks to identify knowledge gaps and misconceptions that may affect early diagnosis and support.

Methodology:

Study Design: Cross sectional online survey

Study Setting: Jinnah hospital, Lahore

Study Duration: 4 months

Data Collection and analysis: A cross-sectional study was conducted from February to May 2025 using an internet-based questionnaire that included the 22-item Dementia Knowledge Assessment Scale (DKAS). Demographic data and responses to all DKAS items were collected. The questionnaire was circulated primarily in urban areas of Pakistan, especially Lahore.

Results: A total of 250 participants 197 (78.8%) were females and 53 (21.2%) males. 72.4% participants were in the age group of 18-40 . 66.4 % had prior dementia knowledge while 44% had acquaintances who had dementia. 25.2% considered dementia as a blood vessel disease, while 44.4% knew that Alzheimer's was the main cause of dementia. A large percentage of people 66% were also aware that dementia does impact one's lifespan. Only 36.8% of people were aware that dementia is not a normal part of the aging process.

Conclusion: The general population has a fair understanding of dementia, and most people are aware that it significantly affects quality of life

INTRODUCTION

Dementia is a complex syndrome characterized by a significant decline in cognitive functions, including memory, thinking, and reasoning, to the extent that it interferes with an individual's ability to perform

daily activities independently. It encompasses a range of symptoms that can vary widely among individuals but typically includes memory loss, confusion, difficulties with language and communication, and

changes in mood and behavior. [1] It is an important cause of disability and death among older adults. [2]. Currently, over 55 million people worldwide are living with dementia, with more than 60% residing in low- and middle-income countries. Each year, nearly 10 million new cases are diagnosed. [3].

Furthermore, it is estimated that there are over 400,000 people with dementia in Pakistan,' reveals the World Alzheimer's Report 2023.

In Pakistan, the epidemiological landscape of dementia is evolving significantly due to various demographic and socioeconomic factors. Currently, it is estimated that there are between 150,000 to 200,000 individuals living with dementia in the country, reflecting a prevalence rate that has increased from 2% to 6% among those aged 65 and older as life expectancy rises [4]. This increase is concerning given that Pakistan has a relatively young population, but the proportion of elderly individuals is expected to grow rapidly, leading to a potential surge in dementia cases by 2050. The country faces numerous challenges in addressing dementia care, including limited public awareness, inadequate healthcare infrastructure, and insufficient research initiatives. Moreover, cultural stigmas surrounding mental health often hinder early diagnosis and treatment.[4] As the population ages and the burden of dementia increases, there is an urgent need for comprehensive public health strategies and resources dedicated to improving dementia care in Pakistan. The lack of knowledge and awareness about dementia is a significant public health issue impacting individuals and communities worldwide. According to a study conducted in Saudi Arabia, most health college students had poor knowledge about dementia and out of a total score of 25, the mean average score of the participants included in the study was 13.68 ± 3.18 . [7]

There is a notable scarcity of studies focused on dementia knowledge and awareness in Pakistan. One significant study titled "Understanding, Beliefs and Treatment of Dementia in Pakistan" involved

interviews with 40 dementia patients and their caregivers across Karachi and Lahore. The findings revealed a widespread lack of awareness regarding dementia and its symptoms, with many participants attributing the condition to factors such as stress, shock, or even black magic. [8]

This research on dementia knowledge and awareness in Pakistan will be highly significant as it aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the public's understanding of dementia within the country. Given the limited research conducted in this area, the study will fill a critical gap by highlighting current knowledge levels, misconceptions, and attitudes surrounding dementia among various demographics.

The study on dementia knowledge and awareness in Pakistan will have practical applications that can significantly benefit individuals affected by dementia and their families. Gaining insight into these beliefs is crucial for reducing stigma and developing effective support strategies in resource-limited settings. By documenting these insights, the study can inform targeted public health campaigns aimed at raising awareness, reducing stigma, and promoting early diagnosis and intervention. This is particularly important in Pakistan, where many individuals attribute dementia to normal aging or stress, leading to delays in seeking appropriate care. The findings will help inform culturally appropriate strategies to improve dementia care and reduce stigma in Pakistan. Furthermore, the research can serve as a foundation for developing policies and programs that enhance support services for individuals living with dementia and their caregivers, ultimately improving their quality of life and access to necessary resources.

Objective:

The objective of my study is:

- To determine the knowledge and awareness level regarding Dementia among the general adult population of Pakistan.

Subjects and Methods:

This study was conducted in Jinnah Hospital Lahore. Data was collected from all over Pakistan using the online platform. This research employs a cross-sectional study design. The study was conducted over a span of 4 months from Feb, 2025 to May 2025. Sample size was calculated using WHO sample size calculator at 95% confidence level, relative precision of 0.05, taking mean population level as 13.68 with standard deviation ± 3.18 . The calculated sample size is 84 and this is the minimum sample size estimated. We have recruited 250 responses for our study.

The sampling technique employed in this study is a non-probability convenience sampling method particularly effective for reaching hard-to-access populations. Initially, a Google Form was utilized to create a Dementia Knowledge Awareness Survey (DKAS) questionnaire. This questionnaire was then distributed through various social media platforms to facilitate widespread participation.

The Dementia Knowledge Assessment Scale (DKAS) is a tool designed to measure knowledge related to dementia across four subscales: causes and characteristics, communication and behavior, care considerations, and risks and health promotion. It has demonstrated strong psychometric properties, including high internal consistency with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85 and subscale reliability ranging from 0.65 to 0.76. The DKAS is suitable for use among diverse populations, including healthcare professionals, students, family caregivers, and the general public. Several studies have validated its effectiveness, detailing its development, reliability, and confirmatory factor analysis results that support its structure as a robust instrument for assessing dementia knowledge. These attributes make the DKAS a valuable resource for informing educational interventions aimed at improving understanding of dementia in various settings. The questionnaire will consist of a total of 27 questions, with 7 focused on demographics and the remaining 20 designed to assess participants' knowledge of dementia. Each

knowledge question will carry equal weight, contributing to a maximum total score of 20 points for the questionnaire. The participants who will obtain a score between 0-7 are considered to have poor knowledge, scores between 8-14 indicate average knowledge, and scores from 15-20 reflect good knowledge. [10]

In addition to online distribution, questionnaires in Urdu were made available in public spaces, such as hospitals. This approach aimed to assess the knowledge of dementia among the less educated segments of the Pakistani population, ensuring inclusivity and a broader understanding of dementia awareness across different educational backgrounds. By leveraging both digital and physical distribution methods, the study seeks to gather diverse perspectives on dementia knowledge and awareness within the community.

The data collection process for this study has utilized a structured questionnaire designed to assess dementia knowledge among participants. This questionnaire was pretested to ensure clarity, relevance, and comprehensibility of the questions, allowing for necessary adjustments prior to actual data collection. It consists of two sections: the first section includes demographic questions aimed at gathering essential background information about the participants, such as age, gender, education level, and prior exposure to dementia-related information. The second section comprises questions based on the Dementia Knowledge Assessment Scale (DKAS), which has been prevalidated to ensure its reliability and validity in measuring dementia knowledge. Each question in this section carries equal weight, contributing to a total score that reflects the participant's understanding of dementia. Informed consent of each participant was taken and confidentiality was maintained. Moreover, all ethical considerations have been adhered to within the study.

Data collected from the DKAS was analyzed using statistical software, SPSS-27. Descriptive statistics

summarize participant demographics and knowledge levels. Comparative analyses were conducted to identify differences in knowledge based on demographic factors such as age, education level, and geographic location. The findings are presented in tables and graphs for clarity and ease of interpretation. The qualitative variable is summarized using frequency percentages and visualized through bar graphs and pie charts. The quantitative variable is summarized by calculating the mean and standard deviation, with histograms used for graphical representation. The relationship between knowledge about dementia (dependent variable) and various demographic characteristics of the study participants (independent variables) was analyzed using the Chi-square test, with a p-value of ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results:

There were a total of 250 participants, all of whom were based in Pakistan, out of which 197 (78.8%) were females and 53 (21.2%) males. 72.4% participants were in the age group of 18-40, while

27.6% participants had an age of 40+. The Occupational groups included health care workers (30%), educators (11.6%), students (20.8%), business professionals (12%), licensed professionals (6.4%), technical workers (3.2%) and unemployed (16%). Out of the 250 participants, 66.4% had prior dementia knowledge while 44% had acquaintances who had dementia. Very few participants (25.2%) considered dementia as a blood vessel disease, while 44.4% knew that Alzheimer's was the main cause of dementia. A large percentage of people 66% were also aware that dementia does impact one's lifespan. Only 36.8% of people were aware that dementia is not a normal part of the aging process. Moreover, most people 41.6% agreed that it is not possible to recover from dementia, while 26.4% are not sure about it. Furthermore, 191 (76.4%) people understood that dementia patients require daily care. Most people 190 (76%) knew that depression can reduce the risk of dementia. Finally, the majority of people 188 (75.2%) knew that dementia requires early diagnosis.

Graph no: 1 Gender distribution among respondents

Graph no: 2 score distribution among respondents

Discussion:

The present study investigated the knowledge and awareness regarding dementia among the general adult population of Pakistan. The results depict that most people had moderate knowledge, while many also had good knowledge and very few had poor knowledge about Dementia. A reason for such results can be that our study was mostly conducted over the urban population of Pakistan, which mostly includes the educated class. More than 40% of people had acquaintances that suffered from dementia, which shows the prevalence of this disease in Pakistan.

According to the study "Public awareness and knowledge of factors associated with dementia in China" by Zheng et al., published in BMC Public Health in October 2020, most participants were unable to identify the risk factors of dementia and showed limited awareness of its protective factors.(6). In contrast, our data indicates that the majority of people in Pakistan demonstrate good knowledge about dementia. This difference may be attributed to the fact that our study focused on an urban population in Pakistan, whereas the Chinese study likely included participants from both urban and rural areas.

The study "Assessment of dementia knowledge among health college students in Saudi Arabia"

reported that the mean dementia knowledge score was 54.7%, indicating generally poor awareness, particularly in the domains of risk and health promotion. In contrast, our data indicates a slightly lower mean knowledge score of 50% among an urban population in Pakistan. This difference may be attributed to the smaller sample size in our study, which could affect the precision of the estimated knowledge level. Additionally, the Saudi Arabian study included a larger and more diverse sample of health college students, whereas our study focused on a smaller urban cohort. These factors may explain the variation in dementia knowledge scores between the two populations. (5)

In a meta analysis done by Cautions et al analyzed surveys conducted in Europe, the US, Eastern Asia, Israel, and Australia. Almost 50% of respondents agreed that dementia is a normal and non-preventable part of ageing, but belief in the potential for prevention may be improving over time. Majority of respondents reported belief in the availability of a cure for dementia. The value of seeking treatment was highly endorsed. The study concluded that knowledge about the potential for dementia prevention and treatment remains poor but may be improving over time. Knowledge among those living in low- and middle-income countries are largely

unknown, presenting challenges for the development of National action plans consistent with World Health Organization directives. (9).

In our study 66.4 % had prior dementia knowledge while 44% had acquaintances who had dementia. Very few participants, 25.2% considered dementia as a blood vessel disease, while 44.4% knew that Alzheimer's was the main cause of dementia. A large percentage of people 66% were also aware that dementia does impact one's lifespan.

The limitation of our study was a small sample size of a diverse population with different beliefs, culture and educational background. The study paved a way for future qualitative study to put more light on this important ageing disorder and help in delineating guidelines for management of patients with dementia.

Conclusion:

The conclusion of my study is that:

- The general population has a fair understanding of dementia, and most people are aware that it significantly affects quality of life.

Conflict of interest:

None

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